

Patients' Expression On Nursing Care in State Specialist Hospitals in Ondo State Nigeria

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Abstract:

Nursing care is what patients encounter during their stay in hospitals, complaints of poor attitude, lack of adequate care, carefree attitude among healthcare workers toward patients appear to be on the increase in government hospitals. The study aimed to explore patients' expression on nursing care in state specialist hospitals, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive phenomenological design to investigate patients' expression on nursing care while on admission. A study population of patients who spent over 2 to 4 weeks on admission and have experienced and interacted with nurses while receiving care. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting 20 participants for this study across the two State Specialist Hospitals at saturation point. The researcher with the help of interview guide conducted an in-depth face to face interview with the participants. The qualitative process of data collection involves interviews, documentation, and observations, using a reliable and valid recording instrument. The data collected were analyzed using MAXQDA. Data analysis strategies consisted of using qualitative software, key words, phrases, and codes, which contributed to identifying three themes and ten subthemes (a) Patients expectations (b) Patients experience and (c) patients satisfaction. The findings indicated that majority of the participants had expected nurses to be kind, cheerful, responsive, honest and

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friendly, and not to be harsh and rude. Most of the participants have positive experiences with the nurses but some respondents have negative experience. Participant also expressed their satisfactions with nursing care. In conclusion, some patients encountered rude or carefree nurses who showed lack of empathy and they were not satisfied with the care rendered. Efforts should be geared towards providing prompt care to all patients irrespective of their disease condition and status.

Keywords: Patients, Patients' Expression, Nursing Care,

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Introduction

Nursing care is vital to patients' experience while on admission bed, and this forms a key part of entire satisfaction. Caring in nursing is a direct service, purpose driven and flexible to suit the yearnings/needs of the patients, responsiveness about the patients' concerns, and hopes, as well as the relative and entire community during illness. The nurse's main responsibility is to those people who require nursing care. Nursing care is connected to patient satisfaction, quality care is what patients seek healthcare services for, rendering patient oriented care thereby making patient feel more humane with self-worth, is the primary aim for those rendering the care (Taiwo, 2014).

Patient satisfaction with nursing care is one of the central determinants of total satisfaction of patients and quality appraisals in hospitals. Nursing care is the foremost experience that patients meet during their stay in hospitals, the qualities of value and moral stand of caring is entrenched in quality of nursing practice and level of proficiency displayed by the nurse through actions taken in responding to the uniqueness of individual ailment state in fulfilling human needs as it constitutes a major part of overall satisfaction (Gandomani, et al, 2018). Patient satisfaction with nursing care is the amount of convergence between the expectations that patient has of ideal care and their opinion of the care that they actually receive (Bernardo, 2017).

Patients' expectation from the nurses and other members of the healthcare team refers to their impression of care provision before hospitalization. Patients' anticipation does not imply the patients' satisfaction with the provided care and services. Satisfaction can only be measured while the patient is on admission and after discharged; at the end, the patients may express a high level of satisfaction when their expectations have been totally met. When expectation of patients is met it enhances compliance to treatment as this improves the physical and mental healing process. Patients become satisfied with care by giving adequate information to the patient about his/her progress, the competence and understanding of nurses in patient education, the waiting time to visit physician, and interpersonal relationship between patient and health personnel are determinants of satisfaction (Batbaatar, Dorjdagva, Luvsannyam, Savino & Amenta, 2017). On the other hand, if expectations are not met, anxiety and stress set in which may invariably delay healing recovery and healing process, prolongs hospital stay, and increases treatment cost (Gandomani, et al., 2018).

Patient satisfaction with nursing care has steadily been found to be associated with overall satisfaction care, satisfaction is a psychological phenomenon, a personal feeling of pleasure and gratification, evaluation of the mental and emotional reaction that result from the patient's anticipation of nursing care and their experience of actual nurse behavior and attributes which manifests itself in the form of certain significant characteristics (attitudes, behaviour, and reactions). Care satisfaction is simply the patient's verdict of the care and treatment received; expectations and total healthcare experience which serves as yardstick in determining the quality of service within the health care systems (Mukhtar, Anjum, Bajwa & Hamid, 2013). Care satisfaction implies the degree to which general health care needs meet patient requirements (Sharma, et al, 2014).

Caring behavior by nurses adds to satisfaction and patient's well-being as nursing staff spend more time with the patients than other health workers. Hence, patient satisfaction is essential

in every therapeutic procedure. Today, determining patient satisfaction is a major part of hospital/clinic management approaches towards improving the quality of care and ensuring that health services meet patients' needs by evaluating the patients experience on services they received globally (Gandomani, et al, 2018). Tang, et al (2013) revealed that staff competence in tackling patient problems, friendliness among health care workers, accessibility of prescribed drugs in the hospital pharmacy, confidentiality during treatment and patient waiting time were important factors influencing patient satisfaction. Hence, it is not only time nurses spent with patients and respect for patients that would determine patients' experience of nursing care but also other factors such as adequate information about their illness and treatment, kindness, cheerfulness, comportsment and among others (Olowe, et al, 2019).

Grievances on poor attitude among health workers toward patients appear to be on the increase in government hospitals. Patients expect attention, understanding, kindness and helpfulness from individuals providing care services; nurses were less interested in explanations about interventions and communication with patients (Goh et al, 2016).

This research therefore explored patients' expression on Nursing Care in State Specialist Hospitals in Ondo State, Nigeria. This study specifically examined:

1. the nursing care received by patients while receiving treatment; and
2. patients' satisfaction with nursing care.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. How would you describe the nursing care you received while receiving treatment in the hospital?
2. How satisfied are the patients with nursing care in state specialist hospitals?

Methodology

This study was a qualitative research which adopted descriptive phenomenological design to explore patients' expression on Nursing Care while on admission. The study population comprised of patients admitted into State Specialists Hospital Okitipupa and Ikare Akoko. The sample size was determined until participants provided no new information (saturation point) on patients' expression of nursing care in state specialist hospitals, Okitipupa and Ikare Akoko. After interview with 20 patients, the researcher reached saturation point. Purposive sampling techniques was utilized in selecting patients who spent over 2 weeks to 4 weeks and above before been discharged from the hospital who have interacted and experienced the care attributes of nurses while receiving care.

The instrument for data collection was In-depth interviews with the aid of interview guide. The interview guide was developed based on the objective of the study and review of related literature on nursing care. The interview was face to face, participants were given nickname to ensure confidentiality. Privacy was ensured, by conducting the interview in isolated area of the hospital. The researcher ensured that interview with participants continued until no new information on nursing care are identified by the participants. Interviews was conducted in English and Yoruba language and lasted between 10 to 15 minutes. The research assistant helped with a voice recorder.

To ensure the integrity in which the study was conducted and the credibility of findings in relation to qualitative research, responses validation and reflexivity was applied during interview and analysis. The voice record interview was transcribed and typed field notes was compared to identify omissions and to ensure that the data on the audio tape are captured accurately in the text. The text was put into a two column table format (first column for text and second column for making notes). The scripts were read through several times by the researcher and the research assistants and brief notes on important information were made in the second column.

The data collected was analyzed using MAXQDA. This was done by listening to voice recordings and transcribing the content verbatim according to themes and footnotes was typed and compared with voice transcription. The transcript was coded by going through the transcript line by line and paragraph by paragraph, to find significant statements and codes.

Results

Question 1: How would you describe the nursing care you received while receiving treatment in the hospital?

Answer

Theme 1 Expectations from Nurses

In other to gain an insight into patients' expectations, participants were asked what their expectation was before coming to the hospital.

Findings from the study shows participant's expectation from nurses is majorly to take good care of them, nurture them to good health, and provide total health care and respect. Some of the participants expected nurses to maintain confidentiality.

Confidentiality

Participants B5 said that *"one of my expectations while coming to this hospital is confidentiality because I am expecting the nurse I am going to meet in this facility to be confidential enough about my health status, about my card and about what I've given them as maybe the sickness. I'm expecting them to be confidential and to keep it between myself and the facility"*.

Acceptance and nurture

Participant B1 responding to question on his expectations while coming to the hospital said *"well 'hmmmm' actually, my expectations are actually. I expected more from them because I believe they're closer to the patient than the doctors, so I believe they should give, they should render more care service to the patient"*. Another participant B2 said that *"To take good care of me and make sure things are done in other to make sure that expectations are met"*. Another Participant B6 stated *"I have expectations that nurses will be up and doing and they will do their job as at when due irrespective of the kind of patient, time, race, status, condition etc. and also expect nurses to render total nursing care to patient without being biased"*.

Findings revealed two of the participants had no expectations when coming to the hospital because they were very sick and can't comprehend what was happening to them and as such don't have any expectations. Participants B7 *"I was not conscious of the environment when coming to hospital, so i had no expectation"*. and B19 *"When I was brought in to the hospital, I was very sick so I had no expectations"*.

Respect

Some other participants expected the nurses to do their job irrespective of the kind of patient, time, race and status while others expected total respect from the nurses.

Warm reception

Participant B20 *"my expectation is that I believed when I see nurses, at least the first thing they should do is to at least give you a warm reception. That is the first thing I expected from any one of them which in that aspect, I will say they did the needful when I took my sister to the hospital, at least they attended to us, at the reception they greeted us and they put on smiling faces"*.

Theme 2: Experience of Patients

The study revealed different responses on the experience of participants with nurses but some of the participants have good experience about their interactions with nurses.

Caring

Participant B1 revealed that *"the nurses have been caring, they have been wonderful. They are doing their job as at when due, and attending to patient though not only the patients they are assigned to even to other patients they've been doing their job and its satisfactory"*. Another participant B3 was so please with a particular nurse that she said *"That one down there, she took me as her father. Yes, she is nice but some of them, some re, maybe the pressure is on them"*. Some other participants expressed their love for nurses due to their experiencing utmost care, participant B6 said *"I love the nurses because if one is done with work, another nurse will take over the work. All the nurses work together. It's not as if it's one man's work, all of them join hands together to work. I also love the way they play together, share the work, do things together and not leaving one person to do all the work. I really appreciate all the nurses for their work"*.

Some of the patients also believed younger nurses attended well to them than older nurses, participant B13 *have good things to say about younger nurses "nurses are actually nice, they did what they could, they had opportunity of doing the best they could at their own best but there was no resources to work which actually hindered the outcome and I also discovered that most younger nurses work harder than those older ones. I guess they're not being trained, the way those younger nurses were handling patient especially my own personal sister was actually so overwhelming and nice but the old ones were just saying what me as a nurse shouldn't be saying"*. Another participant, B5 equally has the same opinion as participant B13, *she said "I can rate their attributes to us patient to some extent, they are trying their best. We are all working towards perfection, so they are work, they are trying and I think this era, these nurses era they are making it better than before because our previous experience with nurses we knew them to be arrogant, shouting on patient, even mentioning patient name openly or you can hear them say patient in room so so so"*.

Friendly

Some participants praised the nurses for their friendliness, participant B11 explained that *"The hospital I visited did well by welcoming their clients in a friendly and heart soothing manner. when I got to the hospital alongside my sister who was sick the manner in which they attended to us even when we haven't presented the hospital card was reassuring and that changed the mentality we were going there with. Even the drugs we were told to get were very affordable and wasn't even up to the price we had in mind"*.

Lack of care

In this regard, some had bad experiences with the nurses, participant B2 said, *my experience "Some still manage to do some things that are good to us and Like many of them don't really show care about and feelings of what you really go through"*.

Lack of attention and responsiveness

B2: *he continued that nurses hardly give attention when needed. Also, participant B4 said of his experience" Some of these 'ehmm' carefree, some of these your colleagues are carefree, they hardly give attention to their duties while we have few that are cheerful and they show concern about the state of those of us that are here but generally some of you are carefree"*.

Also, participant B9 related her experience with the nurses; she said *"During my stay in the hospital, my experiences were not really palatable because the way I expected them to really care that was not what I met. I think the way we say that nursing is caring is what we're thought to do but I think because of the work load that we have on ground, the way they attend to patient is totally different from what I saw actually bringing because what I really expected, when you call them that you need bedpan they will tell you to call your relatives which is not what I expected because in teaching hospitals where I've been, it is nurses that do everything but here is totally different"*.

Patient education

Participant B18 said *"For then, to be honest the medicine that they give, some will give and some will talk to us that the medicine the nature still better, some gives us hope for the condition that we found ourselves, so they are trying and they are doing their best"*

Lack of empathy

Participants B10 also have negative experience with nurses and said that *"When you get there, instead of them to ask you what you're passing through and quickly attend to you, maybe you come in emergency they will just be referring you or ask you to go and take card and whereas somebody is in pain or the case of someone bleeding, instead of them to take preliminary caution and take care of the person before referring them, they won't, uhmm...first impression has weigh me down, when I get to a place and they did not take care of me, the level of damage as a result of abandoning is already there and nobody can take care of that so I'm not satisfied at all"*

Question 2: How satisfied are the patients with nursing care in state specialist hospitals?

Answer

Majority of the participants were satisfied with the nurse's care attributes, 10 participants (50%) were satisfied with the nurses. Participant B1 when asked if he is satisfied with the care he received replied that *"well, ranging between 0-100 on average I will give 65%"*.

Participant B4 *"Yeeeaahh', to certain extent, we derive satisfaction"*.

Also participants B3, B6, B8, B11, B12, B16, B17 and B18 replied to same question that they are satisfied with the care rendered by the nurses.

Four participants (20%) were partially satisfied with the care provided by the nurses. Participant B4 was satisfied to a certain extent with the nurses care provided, he further advised on the area he wants nurses to improve *"The area of human relationship. It's not about the profession but nursing or medical care is beyond nursing or medical care, looking into his eyes, what have you done but you should be able to feel some empathy for the*

patient". Also, participants B5 "said she is partially satisfied and on improvement of nurses she said "we have many nurses, some of them they are nonchalant attitude towards patient, forgetfulness, at times you suppose to use your drugs maybe seven (7) and some of them because they forget and when you ask they will just say madam! we forgot to give you and even the vitals they supposed to be doing, maybe doctors have allocated 4 hourly, 6 hourly, 8 hourly, they were unable to meet up but I can say this, maybe it's because of not enough hands that is affecting them".

Six participants (30%) were not satisfied with the care provided by the nurses at all, participant B2 while expressing that he is not satisfied with the care provided advised "the nurses to "improve on their training" and also have "human management". Participant B10 also echoed same view and said that "first impression has weigh me down, when I get to a place and they did not take care of me, the level of damage as a result of abandoning is already there and nobody can take care of that so I'm not satisfied at all"

Discussion of Findings

Patience Expectations

The study participant revealed their expectations from nurses; these expectations are the characteristics that the patients expected from nurses as they provide nursing care to them. If these expectations are met patients are able to appreciate the quality of nursing care they have received. Majority of the participants expected nurses to be kind, cheerful, responsive, honesty and friendly, and not to be harsh and rude. Other expectations were that they expected nurses to be knowledgeable and competent, communicate to them about the nursing care, inform them and explain treatment, medication and procedures to them as pointed out by a participant "my expectations from the nurses while visiting the hospital is, at least we know nursing is caring, they should be able to care for patient. When you call them they should be able to attend to you because it is the nurses that you see that stays with patients 24hours. I think we should be able to have effective communication and have good interpersonal relationship with them.

The study revealed that almost all participants agreed on expectations of utmost care from nurses except 2 of the participants (10%) who had no expectation because of being very sick and unaware of being brought to the hospital. These findings can be compared with the study findings done in China which found that patients were expecting nurses to be kind, polite and continued care (You, et al, 2013). The findings of this study is also consistent with the study carried out in Turkey on patients expectations of nursing care, where majority of the patients were expecting nurses to be cheerful, knowledgeable and competent, and to be informed of the treatment (Ozan, et al, 2015). Findings from the study were also supported by Baldursdottir and Jonsdottir (2017), whose findings showed that patients who were classified as "non-urgent" had higher expectations than patients in the emergent group. The results of this study indicate that, irrespective of the seriousness of their illness, patients feel the same need to be cared for. Professionals should be aware of this need because there is a tendency to minimize patients' complaints if they are not considered to be seriously ill. Patients are, however, entitled to high quality care, regardless of the professional's perception of the seriousness of their illness.

Experience of Patients

Participants in this study shared their experiences with nurses; a participant applauded “the nurses have been caring, they have been wonderful. They are doing their job as at when due, and attending to patient though not only the patients they are assigned to even to other patients they’ve been doing their job and its satisfactory”

Another participant also applauded a particular nurse saying “That one down there, she took me as her father.”

And another also sing praises of the nurses “the nurses were accommodating and displayed characteristics that they were up to the task that was later before them and they took care of the patients to the best of their capacity and there is cooperation among them and other health care workers like the doctors etc., to ensure that the goal of treatment and management of the case is achieved”.

The participant’s experiences highlighted the importance of nurse-patient relationship in patient satisfaction. Reactions of nurses to patients remained an experience most patients treasure and remembered for long. This concept includes sociable relationship, developed rapport, patients known as people, mutual understanding, respect, trust, honesty, cooperation and humor (Shawa, 2013).

Patients who were satisfied were influenced by nurses who had sufficient time to meet their needs, showed genuine interest in them as persons and thoughtfulness despite the burden of work (Berg & Danielson, 2007).

Some of the participants have negative experience with the nurses. A participant complained that “many of them don’t really show care about you and feelings of what you really go through”. Another echoed “Some of these your colleagues are carefree, they hardly give attention to their duties”. And another participant also has negative experience saying “During my stay in the hospital, my experiences were not really palatable because the way I expected them to really care that was not what I met”.

Therefore, if nurses did not respect patients’ rights such as right to privacy, and right to information, it was easy for patients to conclude that they had a negative nursing experience. Patients needed a lot of information about their conditions, treatment options and procedures. Carrying out nursing activities professionally will also help patients have a positive experience while in the ward.

Patients Satisfaction

The study showed that participants were classified into three categories, those that are satisfied, partially satisfied and not satisfied. Majority of the participants were satisfied with the care rendered by the nurses while 20% were partially satisfied and 30% were not satisfied at all. One of the reasons for dissatisfaction may be that that the patients’ problems were not properly addressed by the nurses. The study was consistent with one study which found that patients reported themselves very satisfied with nursing care (Chaka, 2005). These findings are in contrast with the study that was done in Pakistan. The Pakistan study found that 94% of patients liked nursing practice of keeping privacy of patients and overall patients’ satisfaction of nursing care was 45% and 55% were dissatisfied (You, et al, 2013).

Conclusion

The study assessed patients' firsthand information on their experiences with nurses during admission. The study concluded that patients come to the hospital with high expectations of meeting friendly nurses who will respect and take care of them. Some of the participants came across friendly nurses who take adequate care of them when on admission while other patients encountered rude or carefree nurses who showed lack of empathy and they were not satisfied with the care rendered.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that

- i. Patients' opinion for improving quality of nursing care should be taken into considerations to improve quality of nursing care.
- ii. Annual mandatory educational programme for nurses should be established to update their knowledge of patients' satisfactions.
- iii. Assessment should include patients' care expectations especially at admission so as to incorporate them in the nursing care plan.
- iv. There is need for nurses to establish good rapport with patients in order to promote trust between the nurse and the patient hence reducing the chances of patients labeling nurses as rude people and also will make patients feel at home.
- v. Nurses also need to acquire customer care skills through organized seminars/trainings by the hospital management.
- vi. Nurses should be advocating for patients' rights in the wards. They should be the first ones to respect patients' rights such as right to privacy and information. Patients feel satisfied if their rights are respected.
- vii. The hospital management should consider employing more nurses since some patients felt that they did not receive satisfactory nursing care due to shortage of nurses.

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